

Table 3. Summary of most common mental health outcomes and type and frequency of measures of mental health impact

Five Most Common MH Outcomes	Number of unique measures for that outcome	Three most common measures for that outcome (frequency)
1. Posttraumatic Stress Disorder	22	1. PTSD Checklist for DSM5 (PCL 5) (16) 2. PTSD Checklist (PCL-6) (8) 3. PTSD Checklist - Specific (PCL-S) (7)
2. Depression	15	1. Patient Health Questionnaire - 9 (PHQ-9) (15) 2. Patient Health Questionnaire – 2 (PHQ-2) (6) 3. Depression Anxiety and Stress Scales (DASS-21) (4)
3. Anxiety	13	1. (tied) Generalized Anxiety Disorder – 7 (GAD-7); Generalized Anxiety Disorder – 2 (GAD-2) (6 each) 2. Depression Anxiety and Stress Scales (DASS-21) (4)
4. Psychological distress	4	1. Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6) (7) 2. Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) (3) 3. (tied) Brief symptom rating scale (BSRS-5); General Health Questionnaire Twelve Plus R (GHQ-12-Plus-R) - Items 1-12 (1 each)
5. Suicidal Ideation	10	1. Patient Health Questionnaire – 9 (PHQ-9) final item (2) 2. Interview questions (2) 3. All other tools had a frequency of 1

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